

THE ROLE OF FINANCIAL DERIVATIVES IN HEDGING FINANCIAL RISKS

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Abstract. This article explores the immense importance and relevance of financial derivatives in the context of minimizing and protecting against potential financial hazards. The main focus here is to acquire an in-depth comprehension of the crucial role that these instruments play in mitigating and overseeing risks.

Keywords: financial derivatives, futures, forwards, options, swaps, financial risk, credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, market risk, legal risk, hedging, risk management.

РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ПРОИЗВОДНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РИСКОВ

Аннотация. В этой статье исследуется огромная важность и актуальность производных финансовых инструментов в контексте минимизации и защиты от потенциальных финансовых рисков. Основное внимание здесь уделяется глубокому пониманию решающей роли, которую эти инструменты играют в смягчении и контроле рисков.

Ключевые слова: производные финансовые инструменты, фьючерсы, форварды, опционы, свопы, финансовый риск, кредитный риск, риск ликвидности, операционный риск, рыночный риск, юридический риск, хеджирование, управление рисками.

INTRODUCTION

Financial derivatives are a pivotal component of the contemporary economy, enabling individuals and companies to manage risks, speculate on price fluctuations, and access diverse asset classes. By offering a means to stabilize investment portfolios, safeguard against turbulent market conditions, and enhance financial gains, derivatives serve as a valuable tool for investors to enhance their overall fiscal resilience.

The growth of the derivatives market has assumed an increasingly significant role within the realm of finance, functioning not only as a crucial safeguarding mechanism but also as a valuable source of immediate information, thus enhancing the efficiency of financial market operations. The derivatives market holds an indispensable position in fostering the progress of efficient capital markets. It promotes the seamless movement of capital across borders and fosters greater prospects for portfolio diversification. By enabling and intensifying the accumulation of capital, the advancement of derivatives markets exerts a notable impact on both the financial market and economic advancement.

DEFINITION AND TYPES OF FINANCIAL DERIVATIVES

Definition of financial derivatives

There are numerous interpretations and explanations surrounding the concept of financial derivatives. These definitions may vary based on the context and perspective of various reputable institutions involved in the financial industry.

The International Monetary Fund defines financial derivatives as “financial instruments that are linked to a specific financial instrument or indicator or commodity, and through which specific financial risks can be traded in financial markets in their own right” [1].

The Bank for International Settlements (BIS) provides a similar definition with some specifications on the types of financial risks for mitigation. According to the BIS, a derivative contract is “a financial instrument that is linked to another specific financial instrument or indicator or commodity and through which specific financial risks (such as interest rate risk, foreign exchange risk, equity and commodity price risks, credit risk and so on) can be traded in their own right in financial markets” [2].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the securities market” specify derivatives as “securities issued by legal entities in the form of options, futures on securities, depositary receipts and other financial instruments that certify the rights or obligations of their owners in relation to other securities” [3].

Types of financial derivatives

In the field of finance, individuals and companies come across a wide range of financial derivatives that include futures contracts, forward contract, options and swaps. The classification of these instruments is based on their unique characteristics and operational aspects that are widely observed in the extensive financial market landscape.

Futures contracts

A futures contract is a standardized contract in which both parties agree to purchase or sell the underlying commodity or asset at a predetermined price on a specified future date [4]. They offer a financial tool that allows market participants to effectively manage changes in the value of an asset within a specific period of time.

The purchaser of a futures contract is required to acquire the underlying asset, while the seller is obliged to sell it, with both parties following pre-established conditions regarding price and date. These contracts are actively traded on exchanges, which play a vital role as intermediaries in facilitating transactions between buyers and sellers [5].

Futures contracts offer two forms of settlement: physical delivery or cash settlement. In the case of physical delivery, the buyer receives the underlying asset at the predetermined price and date. Alternatively, cash settlement involves the payment of cash based on the disparity between the spot price and the futures price of the underlying asset [6].

Forward contracts

A forward contract is a financial tool enabling two parties to decide on the buying or selling of an asset on a prearranged date, at a present agreed-upon price. This asset may encompass commodities, currencies, stocks, bonds or real estate [7].

Forward and futures contracts differ in terms of standardization of their specifications and the manner in which they are traded. Futures contracts are traded on exchanges and follow a set standard, whereas forward contracts are typically concluded over-the-counter (OTC), implying that they are customized to meet the specific requirements of the involved parties. Similar to

futures contracts, forward contracts are resolved through the exchange of physical assets or cash settlement [6].

Options

Options are a form of financial instrument in which the purchaser is granted the choice, but not the requirement, to purchase or sell an underlying asset at a predetermined price and date. Exchanges and OTC markets serve as platforms for trading options. These instruments have diverse applications encompassing hedging, speculation, and generating income [6].

There are two primary categories of options: call options and put options. Call options provide the purchaser with the right to purchase an underlying asset at a predetermined price, known as the strike price, by a specified date referred to as the expiration date. On the other hand, put options grant the buyer the right to sell an underlying asset at a predetermined price on or before a specified date [6].

There are two types of options based on their maturity, namely American and European options. The difference between them lies in how flexible they are to exercise. American options provide the benefit of allowing investors to exercise them at any time before the expiration date, giving them more freedom in decision-making. Conversely, European options only allow exercise on the expiration date, limiting investors' ability to take a prompt action [8].

Based on data provided by the Options Clearing Corporation (OCC), the entity responsible for ensuring the integrity of all U.S. exchange-traded options, OCC successfully cleared an unprecedented 10.38 billion contracts in the year 2022, with an average daily volume of 41.3 million contracts [9].

Swaps

A swap contract is a financial instrument that enables the exchange of cash flows associated with an underlying asset between two entities. The underlying asset may encompass diverse items, including but not limited to interest rates, currencies or commodities. Upon mutual consensus, both parties commit to exchanging cash flows for a specified time span, which are determined by the value of the underlying asset. Swap agreements are designed to meet the unique needs of the participants, allowing them to employ swaps to mitigate risks, speculate on future prices, or generate income [10].

There is an extensive selection of swaps available, each designed to counteract a specific form of risk or to achieve profits by capitalizing on expected future price fluctuations. Among the plethora of swap options frequently utilized, the following can be highlighted [11]:

1. *Interest rate swaps* enable parties to interchange fixed-rate payments with floating-rate payments, facilitating flexibility and risk management in financial transactions. For instance, a corporation possessing a loan with a variable interest rate might engage in a swap with another corporation that holds a loan with a fixed interest rate in order to mitigate its susceptibility to fluctuations in interest rates.

2. *Currency swaps* provide the opportunity for parties to exchange payments in one currency for payments in another currency, assisting in mitigating currency fluctuations and enhancing international trade. For example, a company that holds debt in foreign currency could engage in a swap agreement with another company that holds debt in domestic currency thus mitigating its vulnerability to currency fluctuations.

3. *Commodity swaps* offer parties the ability to exchange payments linked to the price of a specific commodity, such as oil or gold, providing a means to manage exposure to commodity price volatility. An instance of this would be a company that opts to exchange its dependence on oil prices by engaging in a mutual agreement with another company specialized in oil production. In this scenario, one party consents to make predetermined payments for each unit of oil and receive the current market price for it. Conversely, the other party will receive the predetermined rate and make payments based on the fluctuating price.

4. *Credit default swaps* enable parties to transfer the potential risk of a loan or other financial obligation default, offering protection and transferring the burden of potential losses to another entity. For instance, an investor may engage in a swap agreement with an insurance company, aiming to safeguard his investment from potential financial setbacks in the event of a specific company's failure to meet its debt obligations.

FINANCIAL RISKS AND THEIR TYPES

Definition of financial risk

Financial risk can be defined as the potential for loss resulting from inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems, or from external events such as market volatility and liquidity constraints ^[12].

In the modern world we live in, the importance of financial risk cannot be emphasized enough due to its crucial role in the global financial system. Financial markets are characterized by intricate complexity and close interconnections, giving rise to a multitude of factors that impact the worth of investments and enterprises, consequently amplifying their vulnerability to risks.

Financial risk can exert a consequential influence on individuals, enterprises, and the global economy as a whole. On an individual level, financial risk has the potential to induce significant financial adversity, leading to distressing outcomes such as bankruptcy or foreclosure. Similarly, businesses face the threat of financial risk, which in turn can result in insolvency or bankruptcy. On a larger scale, the global economy is vulnerable to financial risk, which, if not managed effectively, can trigger recessions and cause financial crises ^[13].

Financial risk can manifest itself as a multifaceted instrument, bearing both advantageous prospects and adverse implications. Individuals possessing a heightened inclination towards risk-taking may stand to reap substantial rewards from their investments. Nevertheless, it is crucial to recognize that those same individuals who willingly indulge in immoderate risk-taking may face the unfortunate repercussion of encountering financial losses ^[13].

Types of financial risks

There are various types of financial risks that encompass a wide range of potential hazards, including credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, market risk and legal risk. These risks are associated with the uncertainties and potential losses that can occur in financial transactions and activities ^[14].

Credit risk

This form of risk emerges when the borrower encounters difficulties in paying back the original amount borrowed or the interest associated with a loan. This risk can be subdivided into two distinct categories, namely default risk and credit spread risk. Default risk pertains to the uncertainty surrounding a borrower's ability to fulfill their repayment obligations. On the other

hand, credit spread risk delves into the difference between the return on an asset deemed to carry a certain level of risk and the return on an asset that is considered risk-free ^[15].

Liquidity risk

Liquidity risk is concerned with the difficulty encountered by an investor when they face challenges in promptly selling their asset that could potentially result in financial losses. This risk can be classified into two specific types: funding liquidity and market liquidity. The aspect of funding liquidity revolves around the investor's ability to access the required funds at a reasonably affordable cost, whereas market liquidity is centered on the investor's capability to sell their asset without inflicting any notable repercussions on its price ^[16].

Operational risk

Operational risk is the possibility of encountering risks due to deficiencies or failures in the internal procedures, individuals, and systems of an organization, as well as external events. This category of risk can be further divided into four distinct groups, namely people risk, process risk, systems risk and external events risk, each with its own unique characteristics and implications ^[17].

People risk specifically pertains to situations where there are shortcomings or failures within the internal processes that involve individuals within the organization. This could include issues such as inadequate training or lack of competence among employees, leading to errors or inefficiencies in the company's operations. It also encompasses risks associated with poor employee behavior or misconduct, which could potentially harm the organization's reputation or lead to financial losses ^[17].

On the other hand, process risk is directly related to insufficiencies or failures in the internal procedures themselves. This could include flaws in the workflow, lack of proper documentation or controls, or insufficient monitoring mechanisms ^[17].

Systems risk, as the name suggests, arises when there are inadequacies or failures in the systems that support the organization's operations. This includes both technological systems, such as software, hardware and network infrastructure, as well as non-technological systems, such as communication channels and organizational structures. When these systems are compromised or malfunctioning, it can lead to disruptions in the company's operations, data loss or breaches in security ^[17].

Lastly, external events risk emanates from factors beyond the company's control. These events can be unpredictable and varied, ranging from natural disasters like hurricanes or earthquakes that may hinder the company's shipping process or cause supply chain disruptions, to political changes that introduce new regulations or restrict certain business activities. This type of risk emphasizes the importance of a company's ability to adapt and respond to external challenges, as well as the need for contingency plans and business continuity strategies ^[17].

Market risk

Market risk refers to the potential risk that emerges from the volatile nature of market prices. This risk can be further categorized into two types: systematic risk and unsystematic risk. Systematic risk is characterized by its influence on the overall market, impacting numerous investments simultaneously. On the other hand, unsystematic risk solely impacts individual securities or specific sectors, thus being more localized in nature ^[18].

Legal risk

Legal risk stems from modifications in laws and regulations which can have an impact on the worth of an investment. This form of risk can be divided into two classifications: legislative and litigation risks. Legislative risks arise due to alterations in laws and regulations that directly influence the value of an investment, whereas litigation risks emerge from legal actions directed towards either a company or an individual ^{[19][20]}.

USING FINANCIAL DERIVATIVES TO HEDGE FINANCIAL RISKS

Financial derivatives have been widely recognized as highly effective tools for managing and mitigating financial risks. Their usage dates back to the 18th century when they were first employed in commodity futures markets in Japan and Chicago. Initially, derivatives were utilized to hedge against price fluctuations in goods by exchanging one position for another. Over time, derivatives evolved to safeguard against the depreciation of foreign currencies. This was particularly important for wholesale exporters who faced significant currency risks and needed to ensure the value of their collections at the time of the foreign trade agreement. To protect themselves from exposure to currency risks, they turned to financial derivatives ^[21].

While derivatives can involve high risks, they are not inherently riskier than spot transactions. From a microeconomic standpoint, derivatives carry similar market risks as the underlying spot transactions they are based on. In terms of risk, derivatives do not introduce any novel risks that do not already exist in cash markets.

The differences in risk only emerge when directly comparing futures transactions to the underlying assets. Pricing derivatives often lack transparency, especially for private investors, as their value is not solely determined by supply and demand, unlike cash market securities. In addition to the price of the underlying asset, other factors such as remaining maturity can play a crucial role in determining the price of derivatives. This complexity can pose challenges for private investors to comprehend. Furthermore, depending on the financial agreement's structure, there may be a risk of requiring additional funds on the maturity date, contrary to the original intention.

Moreover, derivative prices are susceptible to the same stochastic uncertainty as the underlying assets, introducing market risk. However, due to the leverage effect, derivatives can amplify losses, including the possibility of total loss, during negative price movements.

The risk management process proceeds through the following stages ^[21]:

a) *Communication and consultation* – carried out with stakeholders at all levels of the risk management process, while considering the process itself.

b) *Determining the context* – involves establishing the external, internal, and risk management framework within which the subsequent stages will operate.

c) *Identifying risks* – determining when, where, why and how events can be prevented, mitigated, delayed or amplified in order to achieve objectives.

d) *Risk analysis* – identifying and evaluating existing controls, as well as assessing the potential consequences and likelihood of risks.

e) *Risk assessment* – comparing the estimated level of risk with pre-determined criteria, and weighing the trade-off between potential benefits and unfavorable outcomes. This aids in making decisions regarding the scope and nature of risk treatment.

f) *Risk management* – entails the development and implementation of specific, cost-effective strategies and plans to maximize potential benefits while minimizing potential costs.

g) *Monitoring and review reporting* – it is essential to actively monitor the effectiveness of each stage of the risk management process to ensure ongoing progress.

Historically, managing balance sheet risk involved protecting the bank from various risks. However, contemporary practices increasingly rely on off-balance sheet derivative financial instruments such as forwards, futures, options and swaps. With the growing utilization of these derivatives, financial institutions generate higher fees and revenues.

Financial institutions and companies engage in derivative transactions primarily to safeguard themselves from various forms of financial risk associated with their operations. The motivations of market participants entering derivatives transactions vary depending on their perspective. Banks aim to manage market and credit risks for export companies with high currency volatility. They may also engage in market speculation or arbitrage.

On the other hand, companies typically utilize derivatives to mitigate currency and interest rate risks. For example, they may enter into contracts with banks to buy foreign currency in the future or adjust interest rates. If commodities are traded on an exchange, futures contracts can be utilized. Currency options may be purchased if there is an expectation of domestic currency depreciation.

Overall, derivatives provide a more flexible, efficient, and accurate approach to managing risks, reducing market uncertainty, and limiting risks for individual participants and the overall financial and economic system.

CONCLUSION

Risk management is an essential aspect of effective management and is also a legal requirement. As organizations strive to enhance their material, energy and economic capabilities, there is a noticeable trend towards increased risks. This, in turn, leads to more significant and severe consequences when a risky event occurs. It is important to note that the impact of these hazards is not limited to the system environment but often extends to a broader territory, posing a threat to individuals, resources and the environment.

To address this, proactive measures must be taken to eliminate or minimize the causes and effects of risky events, as well as to mitigate losses and address consequences when such events do occur. This forms the foundation of risk management. Risk itself represents uncertainty and the possibility of loss due to unfavorable changes in risk factors. These risk factors encompass all the causes that influence risk but cannot be controlled by organizations directly.

In today's dynamic business environment, organizations face constant changes. They must be capable of quickly adapting to these changes and addressing them effectively. Risk management serves as a valuable tool in anticipating and responding to these changing circumstances. It enables managers to forecast unfavorable events or circumstances that can be averted, align organizational goals, and allocate control procedures and resources to primary activities and associated risks.

The futures contract, developed by financial engineers, is one of the prominent derivative instruments used to mitigate increasing risks related to price and interest rate fluctuations. Futures contracts are derived from specific assets, such as commodities, securities, currencies or stock indexes. Initially, they were intended as purchase agreements with a forward clause, which allowed

for delayed delivery and payment. However, over time, futures and other derivatives have gained an independent market existence separate from the underlying assets. The derivative's value at maturity is now influenced indirectly by the underlying asset, rather than being directly tied to it. Additionally, the impact of the stock market on the derivative's value is not realized until the price difference is determined.

Derivatives offer a significant advantage in terms of risk management since they facilitate the transfer of market and price risks from the underlying asset to the financial derivative through contractual arrangements. Nevertheless, there are also drawbacks associated with derivative financial instruments, including the potential for total loss.

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